

Figure S3: Results of the Assemble Species by Automatic Partitioning (ASAP) analysis where each sequences is delineated into species bins. The colour codes in each bar indicate the species delineated under the 10 best partition schemes. The values in parenthesis on the top of the bars indicate the number of putative lineages followed by the ASAP score.

Note: ASAP is a hierarchical distance-based method to delimit species from a distance matrix. Sequences are successively merged into groups until all sequences form a single group. Each of these merged groups are evaluated as separate partitions. Partitions are evaluated by assessing the probability of a partition (n) from its previous partition scheme (n-1) and the slope of the ranked distance at a given genetic cut-off. **Lower the ASAP score the better the partition.**